

Economy of Pineapple Cultivation: A Case Study of Medziphema Area, Dimapur District, Nagaland

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Abstract: Pineapple (*Ananas Comosus*) is a tropical fruit belongs to Bromeliaceae family, and it is commercially cultivated in India and the north eastern region as a high-value crop. The objective of the study is to evaluate the commercial viability and to examine the challenges and constraints faced by the pineapple farmers in the study area. It is a mixed method using both primary and secondary data. Statistical tables, averages and percentages are the tools used in the study. An average of 25 years' experience in the cultivation of pineapple by the farmers is a testament to its sustainability in the area. However, pineapple farmers are found confronted with drastic price fluctuations due to lack of secured marketing channel. It was also found that majority (52%) of the farmers utilised more than 60% of their earnings from pineapples on children education. Out of the several challenges faced by the farmers, increasing labour charges in hiring labours for farm maintenance has become the greatest challenge for the largest number of farmers. On the constraints identified in our study context, lack of storage facilities poses a serious and grave problem for the largest number of farmers in their farm business.

Keywords Pineapple, Farmer, Cultivation, Challenges, Constraints.

Introduction

The cultivation of Pineapple (*Ananas comosus*) is confined to high rainfall and humid coastal regions in the peninsular India and hilly region of the country. In India pineapple is commercially grown in Kerala, Goa, Karnataka, West Bengal, Tripura, Mizoram, Meghalaya, Assam and Nagaland (Parvejalam et al., 2020). Though the domestic demand for pineapple is quite high, major portion of pineapple produced in India are exported. Pineapple is mostly exported to Nepal, UK, Spain and UAE in the form of fresh fruit as well as canned juice (Afzal et al. 2018).

Pineapple has a high nutritional value as it is a good source of vitamins like calcium, magnesium, iron etc., beneficial for the immune and digestive systems and helpful in the treatment of Dyspepsia, Bronchitis, High blood pressure and Arthritis (Freitas et al. 2015).

An ideal temperature for successful cultivation of pineapple is between 20-36 degrees centigrade with minimum difference between day and night temperatures. It grows well in almost any type of soil with free-draining. There are different varieties of pineapple which are commonly grown all over the world. The most common varieties grown in India are Kew, Giant Kew, Queen, Jaldhup and Lakhat. Among these varieties, Kew/Giant Kew and Queen are commonly grown in the north eastern part of India and are believed to be best suited for this part of the country (Sindhu et al. 2017).

Pineapples are commonly propagated by-

- a) Crown: Commonly used for propagation but in comparison with other propagation material it takes longer time to come into bearing
- b) Sucker: Most commonly used for propagation and plants raised through suckers have vigorous growth and bears into bearing after a year.
- c) Slip: Though it is not common practise, slips are also used for propagation usually when suckers are not available. It takes about three years to bear fruit.

There are three system of planting commonly practised-

- a). Single Row System: Plants are spaced at 30cm apart and row to row spacing is kept at 60cm.
- b). Double Row System: Plants are planted in two rows spaced at 30cm apart while row to row is spaced at 60cm and after every two rows, 90cm trenches are made between the double rows and the soil from these trenches are used for earthing up so that the rows are slightly raised above the trenches. This system is most commonly practiced and is believed to be best suited for north eastern conditions. By using this system, about 40,000-43,000 plants can be accommodated in one hectare area.
- c). Triple Row System: This system is almost similar with that of double row system except that there are rows between the trenches instead of two rows as in double row system.

Background of the study: Pineapple is one of the focus crops of Nagaland and covers an area of 8697 Ha with annual production of 115086 MT (Adm. Report, Department of Horticulture, Govt. of Nagaland 2019-20). It is grown in almost all districts of Nagaland yet Medziphema area comprising of 5 villages, namely, Medziphema village, Khanakhuru village, Pherima village, Moava village and Sochunoma village, under Dimapur district is well known for sustaining the cultivation of pineapples. Generally it is considered as pineapple area in Nagaland because of the fact that almost every household has a pineapple farm. The area is situated at 30 to 50 km from district headquarter, Dimapur.

Nagaland pineapples are best known for their unique taste and high qualitative parameters with almost fibreless pulp, high juice and high total soluble solids (TSS) content. In Medziphema area, pineapples are grown in an average area of 700 Ha per village with an annual production of 8000 to 9000 MT in each village making the total production of the area at 37% of the total state annual production. However, pineapples produced in Medziphema area still lack export to other parts of the country due to lack of marketing information and delivery packaging materials. According to Chairman of Pineapple Farmers Society, Molvom village, Mr. Lenthang Misao, one hectare of pineapple farming requires an investment of about Rs.20,000/- in the first year. This includes the cost of jungle clearing, planting materials/saplings, irrigation/trenches, labour for planting and labour for weed control.

Rationale of the study: Pineapple is a seasonal product but harvested twice a year. In Nagaland, lack of technology and industry linkage limits the utilization of pineapple as a source of raw material. The economy of pineapple cultivation, thus, needs a thorough investigation to reap its full potentials. An attempt has been made in this study to find out the income generation and challenges and constraints faced by the farmers. There have been sustained production of pineapple in Medziphema area but no study has been done to give a comprehensive insight on the economy of pineapple cultivation in the area. It is also pertinent to examine the challenges and constraints faced by the farmers and highlight the potentials for large scale production so that it can play its role effectively in raising the standard of living of the farmers.

Literature Review:

In Guatemala, Medina and Garcia (2005), in their survey on women in postharvest handling and marketing of pineapple and other fruits found out that women who organized joined efforts to sell their crops in larger

scale has turned marginal producers into a lucrative business and has enabled them to build multi-purpose building that became an important center for the community serving as distributing store, training center, and meeting hall. In Ghana, Ninson (2012), examined the pineapple production in the Akwapim South municipal area and found that pineapple farming in the area exhibit constant returns to scale. The major constraints faced were identified to be lack of reliable market, high cost of farm inputs and inadequate credit for production. Similarly, in the study on profitability and constraints of pineapple production in Osun State of Nigeria, Baruwa (2014) revealed that producers were exploited by market intermediaries as their share in the consumer price was very low contrary to the shares of intermediaries. In Nigeria there is inefficient use of available inputs in the production of pineapple with efficiency score of 0.603 and that it is imperative to make production inputs available to pineapple farmers in proportion they can afford (Balogun et al. 2015).

In Southeast Asia, Prayudi (2017) in his analysis of farm in Pineapple in District Ngancar, Kediri, Indonesia, found out that the selling price of the pineapple obtained by farmers was according to the quality of the fruit. The result of the business feasibility test of 0.5 ha and 1 ha was not the same making both patterns equally worth developing. Analogously, Hidayah et al. (2019) examined the profitability of pineapple production among the smallholders in Johor area of Malaysia and concluded that Malaysia needs to focus on farm size, access to credit, input costs and type of variety in order to enhance output and competitiveness in the global market.

In India, Balan (2018) in his work “The Vazhakulam Pineapple” has stated that pineapple being largely exported from the state of Kerala, 80% of the revenue comes from sales outside the state and consumption within the state is just 20% of the whole produce. However, in the case of North Bengal in India, Das et al. (2011) in their study on the status and growth of pineapple production has found that due to constraints like low opportunity cost, low income potentiality, high price fluctuation and labour migration problem, progress of pineapple cultivation in North Bengal zone was not at all encouraging and its performance was far from expectation.

In north eastern region of India, Saloni et al. (2017) in their study on “Pineapple production and processing in north eastern India” observed that there is the tendency of pineapple growers in the region towards selling fresh fruits rather than processing it themselves or supplying to the fruit processing industries. In the case of the state of Meghalaya, Marak et al. (2013) stated that agro-climatic condition of the state favoured cultivation of different horticulture crops and pineapple was one of the most notable of them. However, the study revealed that there is a need to reduce the technological gap among the tribal farmers through the introduction of location specific agricultural technologies which are economically sustainable. In Assam too, Alam et al. (2020) stated that though Assam has the largest area under pineapple cultivation, lack of adequate knowledge regarding modern farm management technique was the major constraints faced by the farmers. Such constraints were also found in the case of Nagaland state by Sharma et al. (2016) who found out that inadequate transport facilities, absence of market information, lack of organization among producers and problems of storage are the major constraints in pineapple production for the farmers cultivating pineapple.

Objectives: The main objectives of the study are:

- 1) To examine income generation and evaluate the commercial viability of pineapple cultivation.
- 2) To find out the challenges and constraints and suggest suitable measures to counter the hurdles ailing the pineapple farmers.

Research Questions

1. Why Nagaland state despite favorable climate and natural resources is unable to exploit pineapple farming desirably?

2. In which way is the farmer supposed to proceed on his own in the future?
3. How more investors and growers can be attracted to venture in pineapple farming?
4. What are the challenges and constraints faced by the pineapple farmers in Nagaland?

Data and Methodology

It is a mixed method research with both primary and secondary data used. Primary data were collected through interviews and structured questionnaires. The sample size consisted of 200 pineapple farmers taking 40 from each of the 5 villages in Medziphema area. Secondary sources include referred journals, books, newspapers and various other publications of the Government of India and Government of Nagaland. Statistical tables, averages and percentages are the tools used for the study.

Results and Discussion:

i). Sample Profile - Age group: The age of respondent is one of the important factors to understand the views about a particular problem. It is an indicator of a person's physical strength. The age of pineapple farmers in the study area varies from 20 to 60 plus years with largest 31.25% of them falling in the active age group 31-40 years. Also, the survey shows similar gender distribution of pineapple cultivators comprising of 55% male and 45% female cultivators.

ii) Educational qualification: The study shows that 12% of pineapple cultivators are illiterate, 49% of the cultivators have studied up to 10th standard, 18% have completed their matriculation, 12% have completed their higher secondary and 10% of the cultivators have completed their undergraduate degree & above. This shows that farming is no more the domain of the illiterate. The survey also shows most of the farmers are family oriented as 79% of the cultivators are married, 19% of them unmarried and only 2% of the cultivators are divorced.

iii) Household Size: The study shows that by and large, farmers have large family size with 47.5% of them having 4-6 members in a family, 26.25% of them having 7-10 members and 15% of them with 10 plus members while only 11.25% of households having 3 members.

iv) Types of labour: In spite of large family sizes, large majority of the farmers (71.25%) depend on hired labours for their pineapple cultivation. While a small percentage (20%) of farmers solely uses own (family) labour, a meagre 8.75% of the farmers hire labours as well as own (family) labour in cultivating pineapple. The reason for large majority of farmers depending on hired labours is due to the pursuit of formal education of their children.

v) Experience: The number of years of cultivation not only signifies the experience level of farmers but also shows its significance in economic sustainability. With large majority of the farmers (72%) cultivating pineapple for more than 20 years and 28% of them for than 30 years is a sufficient testament to its sustainability in the area. It was also found that 63% of the farmers cultivate on their own land while 17% of them cultivate on leased basis at nominal rate which varies from individual land owners.

vi) Price fluctuation: Though harvested twice a year, pineapple farmers are confronted with drastic price fluctuations due to lack of secured marketing channel. Pineapple been perishable, the study shows farmers compromised 30% of their produce between Rs. 5-20 per kg. during peak season. While a major junk, 61.25%, of their produce gets sold out in the range of Rs 20-40 per kg., a meagre 8.75% of their produce gets sold out at above Rs 40 per kg. only during the lean period (Table 1.1).

Table 1.1: Price fluctuation (in %)

Price per kg. (Rs)	Compromised percentage
05-10	10
10-20	20
20-40	61.25
Above Rs 40	8.75

Source: Field Survey June-July 2020

vii) Types of Market: With major district road and state highway passing through all the 5 villages of the study area, the study revealed that 25% of the farmers sell 30% their pineapple by the road side in the village itself at a range of Rs 30-60 per kg. While 44% of the farmers sell 50% of their produce through middle men at wholesale price ranging from Rs.20-40 per kg., a good percentage of farmers, 31% of them, sell 20% their produce directly to the processing units at wholesale price ranging from Rs.20-30 per kg (Table 1.2).

Table 1.2: Types of Market and Quantity sold at different Price Ranges (in %)

Marketing channel	Farmers (%)	Quantity (%)	Price Ranges/kg. (Rs.)
At village	25	30	30-60
Middle men	44	50	20-40
Processing units	31	20	20-30
Total	100	100	

Source: Field Survey June-July 2020

viii) Major Destination: The study revealed that out of the total 75% of the farmers selling 70% of their total produce outside the village (Table 1.2) has 3 major destinations where pineapples are supplied. It was revealed that almost equal number of farmers, 14% and 15% respectively, sent their produce on wholesale to popular roadside pineapple vendors on National Highway 29 at Medziphema and Journapani. While 38% sent their produce on wholesale to various markets and processing units in Dimapur, 33% of the farmers sell their produce on wholesale to neighbouring state Assam (Table 1.3).

Table 1.3: Major Destination (in %)

Destination	Percentage
Medziphema Town	14
Dimapur	38
Journapani (NH)	15
Assam	33
Total	100

Source: Field Survey June-July 2020

ix) Expenditure pattern: The study also revealed that high majority, 65% of the farmers have taken up pineapple cultivation as their primary source of income and the rest 35% of them as subsidiary income. As such, it is observed that majority, 52% of the farmers utilised more than 60% of their earnings from pineapples on children education while a meagre 5.5% and 5% of the farmers spent less than 30% and 30-60% of their income on children education respectively. A total of 30% farmers utilised their income from pineapples on their daily household expenses while only 8.75% of the farmers use it on other needs.

xii) Quantity Harvest: The study observed that during summer, 41.25% of the farmers reap around 70-100 quintals of pineapples, 22.25% of the farmers reap around 100-180 quintals, 20% of the respondents reap

around 180-220 quintals and 16.25% of them reap above 220 quintals (Table 1.4). However, as revealed in Table 1.4 , the quantities of pineapples reaped during winter season are less compared to summer season.

Table 1.4: Quantity Harvest (in %)

Summer		Winter	
Quantity (Quintal)	%	Quantity (Quintal)	%
70-100	41.25	20-70	73.75
100-180	22.5	70-100	12.5
180-220	20	100 -150	7.5
Above 220	16.25	Above 150	6.25
Total	100	Total	100

Source: Field Survey June-July 2020

xiii. Aid and Training: The study found that 93% of the farmers have not received any training or fund from any Government department or agency. It has been found that organisations like the Molsang Society and various line departments such as Agriculture College at Medziphema, Horticulure and Agriculture Departments and Rural Development Department has neglected the area for long in providing trainings and funds to the cultivators since only 7% of the respondents has received some trainings or funds from the Government for pineapple cultivation.

xiv. Farm Size: The production of pineapple depends on the farm size and the study found that majority, 56.25% of the farmers cultivate pineapple on a size of more than 2 acres. While a mere 10% cultivates on land area less than 1 acre, a substantial 33.75% of them cultivate on an area of 1-2 acres. The study also found that due to lack of knowledge of their usages farmers do not use chemicals like pesticides, chemical fertilizers, herbicides, etc., and only uses of organic manure.

x. Income Generation: The study shows that combining the winter and summer season harvests, majority of the pineapple cultivators i.e 52.50% earn more than ₹10.00 lakh annually while 8.75% of the farmers earn around ₹ 5.00-10.00 lakh, 18.75% of the farmers earn around ₹1.00- 5.00 lakh and 20% of the farmers earn less than ₹1.00 lakh from the pineapple cultivation (Table 1.5).

Table 1.5: Annual income generation from pineapple cultivation (in Rs. lakh).

Annual Income	No. of Farmers (in %)
Below 1.00	20
1.00-5.00	18.75
5.00-10.00	8.75
10.00 and above	52.50
Total	100

Source: Field Survey June-July 2020

Challenges and Constraints Faced by the Pineapple Cultivators:

There are several challenges and constraints faced by the farmers in pineapple cultivation. Starting a farm is an achievement in itself, but maintaining one is the larger challenge. Challenges are those obstacles that a farmer faces but are within the control of an individual and can be overcome by sheer commitment and dedication. Overcoming any challenge that arises is what sets a farmer to grow and sustained production. Some of the challenges identified in our study context are: (1) Farm maintenance/ Hiring labours (2) Farm Fencing (3) Robbery (4) Expansion (5) Market strategy and (6) Financial management. The study revealed that there are varied results on facing various challenges by pineapple farmers in the study area (Table 2).

As 71.25% of the farmers depend on hired labours for their pineapple cultivation (point iv above) due to the pursuit of formal education of every child in a family coupled with increasing labour charges, hiring labours for farm maintenance has become the greatest challenge for the largest number of farmers (42%). In the second position is financial management at 22% which is indicative of the fact that farmers continue to lack financial education on key areas such as cash flow, profit margins, costs reduction, credit management, setting goals, having a practical budget, tracking income and expenses, and making smart investment decisions, etc. The challenge of tackling robbery comes in 3rd position at 13%. This is due to the fact that the study area (Medziphema area) is now inhabited by heterogeneous group of people comprising of different Naga tribes, Kukis, Meiteis of Manipur, Nepalese and Bangladeshi labourers placed on hired basis. In the 4th position is the challenge to expand where 10% of the farmers had been found desirous to expand their farm size. Farm fencing stands in 5th position at 8% which is due to robbery and destruction by cattle and other domesticated animals in the villages. Lastly, for a mere 5% of the farmers, marketing strategy has been found as a challenge. This is due to the fact that farmers continue to lack awareness on the challenge to market to potential customers effectively while retaining the existing customers and don't consider facing the unknown best way to market their products as a challenge (Table 2).

Table 2: Challenges and Constraints in Pineapple Cultivation

Challenges	No. of Farmers (in %)	Constraints	No. of Farmers (in %)
Farm maintenance	42	Price fluctuations	16
Farm Fencing	8	Transportation	2
Robbery	13	Storage	48
Expansion	10	Marketing channel	6
Financial Management	22	Multiple taxations	8
Market strategy	5	Processing Unit	20
Total	100		100

Source: Field Survey June-July 2020

Every farmer has its own unique set of constraints that collectively influence its profitability and competition in the market. Farmer's constraints are generally the external forces they face and try to contend in order to improve their profitability. Some of the particular constraints identified in our study context that affect the farmers are: (1) Price fluctuations (2) Transportation (3) Storage (4) Marketing Channel (5) Multiple Taxations (6) Processing Unit. The study reveals that there are varied results on facing the various constraints by pineapple farmers in the study area (Table 2).

The study revealed that almost half of the famers, i.e., 48%, feel that lack of storage facilities poses a serious and grave problem for their farm business. Storage facilities can be either government provided or privately owned and lend on rent or hire basis which is much required for perishable products like pineapples. However, it is a known fact that provision of high-tech storage facilities is beyond the capacity of the marginal farmers compelling them to compromise their prices easily. Similarly, in the second position is the lack of existence of processing unit which 20% of the farmers felt it a serious constraint for their farm business. In the third position is the unfavourable price fluctuations sometimes artificially manipulated by monopsonistic exploitations which 16% of the farmers felt a serious constraint for their farm business. In the fourth position is the imposition and collection of multiple taxations on any business venture in Nagaland in the form of both legal by municipal and town councils and illegal by insurgent groups. The study revealed that still 8% of the farmers felt that multiple-taxation is the greatest constraint

hampering profitability and growth of their farm business. In the fifth position, 6% of the farmers felt that besides the traditional roadside selling on the highways and long acquainted middlemen, lack of other marketing channel poses a serious constraint for them. Lastly, with proximity to national highway and state highway passing through the area and improved transport system, a mere 2% only of farmers felt lack of transportation as a constraint for their farm business.

Findings:

The study revealed that most of the pineapple farmers are in the active age group 21-50 years with almost equal gender distribution and having an average of 25 years' experience in the cultivation is a testament to its sustainability in the area. While about 50% of the cultivators have studied up to 10th standard, 10% of them with undergraduate degree & above prove that farming is no more the domain of the uneducated people. On the count of family size of the farmers, it still exhibits typical tribal family with an average of 6 members per household with 63% of them cultivating on their own land but large majority (71.25%) of them depend on hired labours. The pineapple farmers are also found confronted with drastic price fluctuations due to lack of secured marketing channel. While 30% of their produce gets sold out at the village on the road side and 70% through middle men, during peak season they compromised 30% of their produce between Rs. 5-20 per kg. and only a meagre 8.75% of their produce gets sold out at above Rs 40 per kg. during the lean period. In an average each households harvests 180-200 quintals annually with majority (52.50%) earning more than ₹10.00 lakh annually, it was also found that majority (52%) of the farmers utilised more than 60% of their earnings from pineapples on children education. However, till date 93% of the farmers have not received any training or assistance from any Government department or funding agency.

On the challenges and constraints, the study revealed that out of the several challenges faced by the farmers, increasing labour charges in hiring labours for farm maintenance has become the greatest challenge for the largest number of farmers. On the constraints identified in our study context, lack of storage facilities poses a serious and grave problem for the largest number of farmers in their farm business.

Suggestions

- 1). Measures should be taken to promote cultivation of pineapples by replacing the use of traditional tools with modern labour-saving tools.
- 2) To enable farmers to produce on a large scale, possible financial assistance should be extended to them especially by rural development department which extends financial assistance on projects ensuring sustainable income generation.
- 3) Steps should be taken by the authorities concerned in setting up marketing facilities and explore marketing avenues so that farmers are protected from any sorts of exploitation by middlemen.
- 4) If not for every village, at least for a cluster of villages, a high tech cold storage should be set up to reap the full potentials of pineapple farming.
- 5) While sustaining its organic nature, proper awareness should be made through trainings about the availability and usage of various modern tools and organic fertilizers and pesticides so as to enhance its productivity.
- 6) More research needs to be conducted by scholars and the line departments of horticulture and agriculture to promote pineapple production.

Conclusion: Having favourable climate and natural soil conditions pineapple farming in Nagaland can be made more lucrative to inspire more and more investors and growers to venture in this field. There is

needed to make cultivators aware of recent developments in the field of pineapple processing and related value added products. Political will is required to overcome the constraints of technology and industry linkages which has been limiting the utilization of pineapples as a source of raw material and avoid post-harvest losses in the form of prices getting compromised below the margin. With enhanced infrastructure, credit facilities, transport assistance and international market access; pineapple farming can play a significant role in boosting economic growth of the state. The Central Institute of Horticulture (CIH), Medziphema, Nagaland, set up in 2006, along with other line departments of the state government should play a more proactive role in working closely with the pineapple growers in facilitating the farmers from production to processing to market promotion.

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